

at maximum tillering and flag leaf stage were significantly lower on plants in potash-treated soil than on those grown in soil containing less K, indicating that plants grown in soil with 183 ppm or

more K are more BB resistant. Percentage of filled grains was significantly lower in plants grown in soil containing less K than in those with added potash. Although yield was not significantly differ-

ent between treatments, plants grown in the soil with 349 ppm added K yielded nearly 16% higher than those grown with 100 ppm K. □

Optimum age of rice for brown spot (BS) control by fungicide spray

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BS, caused by *Cochliobolus miyabeanus* (Ito and Kuribay) Dickson, is a major rice disease in Tamil Nadu. In North Arcot District, foliar application of various

fungicides often does not control the disease.

We sought to determine optimum plant age for fungicide application to control BS in the field. Five treatments were in a randomized block design with four replications (see table). Disease intensity was scored as 0 = no disease, 1 = less than 1% of leaf area affected, 2 = 1-3% affected, 3 = 4-5%, 4 = 6-10%, 5 = 11-15%, 6 = 16-25%, 7 = 26-50%, 8 = 51-76%, and 9 = 76-100%.

Trials from Aug 1981 to Jan 1982 with Ponni and ADT35 showed that spraying edifenphos at 500 ml/ha at 50 and 65 d after transplanting (DT) effectively reduced disease intensity and significantly increased yield. From Nov 1981 to May 1982, spraying Vaigai and Bhavani 25, 40, and 55 DT also was effective. Spraying TKM9 and ADT31 from Apr to Aug 1982 did not produce significantly different yields although all treatments significantly reduced disease intensity (see table). □

BS intensity and mean yield, Tamil Nadu, India.

Age (DT) at spraying	Aug 1981-Jan 1982				Nov 1981-May 1982				Apr-Aug 1982			
	Ponni		ADT35		Vaigai		Bhavani		TKM9		ADT3 1	
	Intensity (mean)	Mean yield (t/ha)	Intensity (mean)	Mean yield (t/ha)	Intensity (mean)	Mean yield (t/ha)	Intensity (mean)	Mean yield (t/ha)	Intensity (mean)	Mean yield (t/ha)	Intensity (mean)	Mean yield (t/ha)
20, 35	7.0	4.4	3.0	2.7	5.0	8.0	6.0	6.1	2.0	4.8	2.0	2.5
35, 50	4.0	5.0	2.0	2.7	5.0	8.1	5.0	7.4	2.0	4.8	2.0	2.6
50, 65	2.0	5.7	1.0	3.3	4.0	7.9	5.0	7.1	2.0	4.7	2.0	2.5
25, 40, 55	3.0	5.2	1.0	3.1	3.0	9.5	3.0	7.8	1.0	4.8	2.0	2.5
Control	9.0	4.1	3.0	2.6	8.0	5.7	8.0	4.6	2.0	4.7	3.0	2.5
CD (P = 0.05)	2.6	0.3	9.8	0.1	2.4	0.8	0.5	0.9	0.4	NS	0.5	NS

Pest Control and Management

INSECTS

Entomopathogenic microorganisms of rice planthoppers and leafhoppers in China

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We studied pathogenic microorganisms of rice planthoppers and leafhopper pests in Hunan Province, China. Under optimum temperature and humidity, the pathogens significantly decrease pest populations. The fungal species usually are most abun-

dant in rainy season and at later stages of rice growth. Up to 80% of the hopper population may be infected. At some sites there are high infection levels by entomopathogenic nematode species such as *Amphimermis unka*.

Various species of pathogenic fungi, two nematode species, and one species of bacterium have been identified as infecting hoppers. Several of the fungal species and the bacterium have been isolated on artificial solid media. The nematodes were identified under the microscope.

The following planthoppers and leafhoppers were examined: *Nilaparvata*

lugens, *Sogatella furcifera*, *Nisia atrovonosa*, *Laodelphax striatellus*, *Saccharosydne procerus*, *Nephotettix cincticeps*, *Empoasca subrufa*, *Deltocephalus dorsalis*, and *Macrostelus fascifrons*. The following entomopathogenic fungi were isolated from them: *Entomophthora delphacis*, *Beauveria bassiana*, *B. tenella*, *Metarrhizium anisopliae*, and *Hirsutella saussurei*. Unidentified *Paecilomyces* spp., *Cephanosporium* spp., etc. also have been isolated. Surprisingly, several hoppers were infected with *Nomuraea rileyi*, a common entomopathogen of lepidopteran larvae in the rice ecosystem.